

Research Article

Aquifer Transmissivity, Dar Zarrouk Parameters and the Direction of Flow of Suspended Particulate Matter in Boreholes in MOUUAU and the Kwa Ibo River Umudike-Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to assess the direction of groundwater flow and the extent of interaction of the groundwater within the premises of Micheal Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike(MOUUAU) and the Kwa Ibo River, Umudike - Nigeria. The pattern of groundwater flow within the study locations was obtained through the use of hydraulic heads which were determined using Global Positioning System (GPS). Fourteen (14) VES were taken in four traverses within the premises and immediate environment of MOUUAU in order to determine the aquifer parameters such as conductivity, Dar Zarrouk parameters, transmissivity and the $K\sigma$ values of the study area. The VES data were interpreted using Resist software that works on the least-square inverse modeling technique which employs the backward difference resistivity transforms to obtain the final model for each VES. The electrical conductivity of the study area ranges from $0.00014\Omega^{-1}$ to $0.00014\Omega^{-1}$, hydraulic conductivity $K=8.00\text{m/day}$, the transmissivity ranges from $20.80\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ to $384.80\text{m}^2/\text{day}$. Water samples were taken from boreholes within the premises of MOUUAU and along the banks of Kwa Ibo River bordering the University. The water samples were analysed for physical and chemical properties. Suspended particulate matter load at the College of Natural and Applied Sciences (CNAS) and Zennith bank locations were 1200mg/L and 700mg/L respectively which is above World Health Organisation (WHO) standard. These high values suggest contamination. Based on the pattern of flow and the determined values of particulate matter, the interaction of the Kwa Iboe River and the boreholes were also found to occur at CNAS and the Zennith bank within the study area. Generally, the flow is from north to south of the study area. The pattern and distribution of each parameter was contoured using Surfer 8 softwares. The flow pattern and distribution actually show the direction of flow and the actual position of groundwater interaction between the water in the boreholes and the water from the Kwa Ibo River. Specifically, the analysed data constrained with borehole within the area suggests that the area has top laterite sands underlain by sandy geomaterials.

Key words: Transmissivity, Electrical Conductivity, The Direction of Flow, Suspended Particulate Matter , Boreholes in MOUUAU, Kwa Ibo River , Umudike-Nigeria

Introduction

The knowledge of aquifer parameters is essential for the management of groundwater resource. The parameters, which describe the dynamics of aquifers, include; geometry of the pore space, geometry of the rock particles themselves, secondary geologic processes such as faulting and folding and secondary deposition. All these parameters jointly affect the rate and pattern of groundwater flow.

SPM in earth sciences refers to suspended Particulate Matter. Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) is "...sediment carried in suspension by the turbulent components of the fluid or Brownian movement (Wilber 1983). It is the residue in a well-mixed sample of water that will not pass through a standard, glass fibre ($0.45\mu\text{m}$) filter. Suspended sediments can also be called, suspended solids or suspended particles. Generally, the suspended loads in flowing water consist of grains less than 0.5mm in diameter. There are various types of suspended sediment. Eroded soils produce the most important type of suspended solids on a large scale. Samples of eroded soils include sand, silt and clay that are relocated by rainfall and overland flow and carried into rivers, forest, and urban areas. Organic suspended particulates compose a significant part of suspended solid in most natural waters. By convention, particulate matter (PM) in suspension is defined as the material that is retained on a $0.4 - 0.5\mu\text{m}$ pore size filter. Smaller material is considered to be dissolved. Muddy sediments consist of clays and some variable

silt content and particle diameter (Pugh, 1987) is $< 62.2 \mu\text{m}$. Suspended particulate matter (SPM) regulates the transport of all types of water pollutant in dissolved and particulate phases in Lakes, river and coastal areas, regulates water clarity and sedimentation. Groundwater flow modeling is generally defined as the quantity of groundwater available or direction of dissolved contaminant migration. It is also used to define the limit of a capture zone, for a contamination recovery well (or well field), or for delineating a water well protection area (or recharge area) for a water supply. (Igboekwe and Udoinyang, 2011)

The objective of this paper consists of presenting a suspended matter flow model to simulate the transport of sediments by the Kwa Ibo River- Umudike into the borehole wells in MOUAU. This is an interesting problem since a complex intrusion process occurs when a freshwater input runs into marine waters. To achieve this objective, characterization of the geological formations within the area through interpretation of geophysical data, hydrogeological analysis for aquifer characteristic and groundwater flow modeling of the area have been carried out.

Kwa Ibo River, Umudike-Nigeria lies within the Ikwano and Umuahia South Local Government Areas and was selected for detailed aquifer characterization and hydrogeological investigation. The location map of the study area is in fig.1.1. The Kwa Ibo River watershed is located between latitudes $5^{\circ}19'$ and $5^{\circ}30'$ N and longitude $7^{\circ}30'$ and $7^{\circ}37'$ E . It covers a rectangular area of about 180Km^2 . Also Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike can be located at the latitude of $5^{\circ}28.658'N - 5^{\circ}29.176'N$ and longitude of $7^{\circ}32.256'E - 7^{\circ}32.803'E$. The location map of the University can be obtained in fig1.1

Fig 1.: Map of the study area

Modelling of the suspended particulate matter by the kwa Ibo River was carried out using the interpretation of the geophysical data within the area and some parameters from hydrogeological analysis of aquifer characteristics of the wells located within the area. This enabled us to estimate the water quality of those wells and also the direction of solute contaminant migration.

Solute Transport Modelling

TYPICAL MODELLING LAYOUT

Fig 2: Typical modeling layout

Groundwater quality reflects substances that are dissolved or suspended in the water. Suspended materials are not transported far in most subsurface materials, but it is usually filtered out. In general, groundwater flow is very slow and depends on the permeability (water transmitting ability) of the subsurface materials, as well as the hydraulic gradient (slope of the water-table or pressure gradient for artesian conditions). Fig. 2 shows a typical modeling layout.

FLOW AND TRANSPORT PROCESSES

The process of groundwater flow is generally assumed to be governed by the relations expressed in Darcy’s Laws and the conservation of mass. Darcy’s Law is a phenomenologically derived constitutive equation that describes the flow of a fluid through a porous medium based on the results of experiments on the flow of water through beds of sand. It states that the rate of flow is directly proportional to the drop in vertical elevation between two places in the medium and directly proportional to the distance between them.

$$Q = \frac{KA(H_1 - H_2)}{L} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

- Q = ground water flow rate
- (H₁ - H₂) = piezometric water elevation
- A = Cross sectional area, A
- L = distance between wells

The development of mathematical equations that describes the groundwater flow and transport process may be developed from the fundamental principle of conservation of mass of fluid or of solute. Given a representative volume of porous medium, a general equation for conservation of mass for volume mass is expressed as:

Rate of mass inflow – (rate of mass outflow + rate of mass production/consumption) = Rate of mass accumulation -
----- 2

This statement of conservation of mass (or continuity equation) may be combined with a mathematical expression of the relevant process to obtain a different equation describing flow of transport (Bear 1997, Domenico and Schwartz, 1998; Freeze and Cherry, 1979).

The rate of flow of water through a porous media is related to the properties of the water, the properties of the porous media and the gradient of the hydraulic head, as represented by Darcy's Law which can be written as;

$$q_i = -k_{i,j} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_j} \text{----- 3}$$

Where: q_i = Specific discharge, LT^{-1}
 $k_{i,j}$ = hydraulic conductivity of the porous medium
 LT^{-1} and h = hydraulic head, L

A general form of the equation describing the transient flow of a compressible fluid in a non-homogeneous anisotropic aquifer may be derived by combining Darcy's Law with the continuity equation. A general groundwater flow equation may be written in Cartesian coordinate as;

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[k_{i,j} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_j} \right] = S_s \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + W^* \text{-----4}$$

Where: S_s is the specific storage, LT^{-1} , t is the time, x_i are Cartesian coordinates, W^* is the volumetric flux per unit volume.

If the aquifer is relatively thin compared to its lateral extent, it may be appropriate to assume that groundwater flow is really two-dimensional. This allows the three-dimensional flow equation to be reduced to the case of two dimensional areal flow for which several additional simplifications are possible. An expression similar to equation 4 may be derived for the two-dimensional areal flow of a homogeneous fluid in a confined aquifer and written as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[T_{i,j} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_j} \right] = S \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + W^* \text{----- 5}$$

Where $T_{i,j}$ is the transmissivity. L^2T^{-1} and $T_{i,j} = K_j b$
 b = Saturated thickness of the aquifer, L
 S = Storage Coefficient (dimensionless) and

$W = W^* b$ is the volumetric flux per unit area. When the equation 5 is applied to an unconfined (water table) aquifer system, it must be assumed that the flow is horizontal and equipotential lines are vertical, that the horizontal hydraulic gradient equals the slope of the water table and storage coefficient is equal to specific yield (S_y) (Anderson and Woessner, 1992).

SOLUTE TRANSPORT EQUATION

An equation describing the transport and dispersion of a dissolved chemical in flowing groundwater may be derived from the principle of conservation of mass, equation (2), just as the general flow equation was derived (Bear, 1979; Domenico and Scharz, 1998, Konikow and Groove, 1977, Igboekwe and Udoinyang ;2011, Reddel and Sunada, 1970).

A generalized form of the solute transport equation is presented by Groove (1976), in which terms are incorporated to represent chemical reaction and solute concentration both in the pore fluid and on the solid surfaces as

$$\frac{\partial(qC)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\varepsilon D_{ij} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_j} \right] - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\varepsilon C V_i) - C^1 W^* + CHEM \dots 6$$

Where CHEM equals;

$-\rho_b \frac{\partial \bar{C}}{\partial t}$ for linear equilibrium controlled sorption or ion exchange,

$\sum_{k=1}^c R_k$ for S chemical rate controlled reaction and or

$-\lambda(\varepsilon C + \rho_b C)$ for decay and where;

$D_{i,j}$ is the coefficient of hydrodynamic dispersion, $L^2 T^{-1}$

C^1 is the concentration of the solute in the source or sink fluid, \bar{C} is the concentration of the species absorbed on the solid (mass of solute/mass of solid) ρ, ρ_b is bulky density of the sediment, ML^{-3} ,

R_k is the rate of production of the solute in reaction K, $ML^{-3} T^{-1}$

λ is the decay constant (equals to $\ln \frac{2}{T_{1/2}}$, T^{-1} (Groove, 1976)

TRANSMISSIVITY AND DAR ZARROUK PARAMMETERS

Transmissivity is a measure of the amount of water that can be transmitted horizontally by a full-saturated thickness of the aquifer under hydraulic gradient. The relationship between transmissivity and hydraulic conductivity is given by the relation;

$$T = bk \text{ (m/day)} \quad m = m^2 \text{ day} \dots 7$$

Where b = saturated thickness of the aquifer in meters in

K= hydraulic conductivity in m/day

The study area has aquifer thickness of about 88.0m, hydraulic conductivity of about 8.00m/day and a transmissivity of about 704.00m²/day (Igboekwe, Okwueze and Okereke, 2006).

HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY

Hydraulic conductivity is a measure of the ease with which sediments can transmit water,

Mathematically the unit is given as

$$K = \frac{-V}{\frac{dh}{a}} = \frac{-m/day}{\frac{m}{m}} = m/day$$

i.e. a medium has a unit hydraulic conductivity, if it will transmit in unit from a unit volume of ground water at the prevailing kinematics velocity.

To obtain a layer parameter, a unit square cross sectional area is cut out of a group of n- layers of infinite lateral extent. The total transverse resistance R is given by

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^n h_i \rho_i \dots 8$$

For a horizontal, homogenous and isotopic medium

$\rho = \frac{(R_1 - R_2)}{(h_1 - h_2)}$ Where h_1 and ρ_1 are respectively the thickness and resistivity of the ith layer in the section. The total longitudinal conductance S is

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{h_i}{\rho_i} \dots 9$$

The longitudinal layer conductance Si can also be explained by

$S_i = \sigma_i h_i$ Where σ_i is the layer conductivity. Conductivity in this case is analogous to the layer transmissivity T, given by

$$T = K_i h_i \quad \text{-----} \quad 10$$

K_i is the hydraulic conductivity of the i th layer of the thickness h_i . R and S of the above equation are called the Dar Zarrowk parameters, which have been shown to be powerful interpretational aid in groundwater surveys (Zohdy et al, 1974)

According to the fundamental Darcy's Law, the fluid discharge, Q , is given by

$$Q = KIA \quad \text{-----} \quad 11$$

Where K is the hydraulic conductivity, I is the hydraulic gradient, A is the Cross-sectional area per perpendicular to the direction of flow. The differential form of Ohms Law gives

$$j = \sigma E \quad \text{-----} \quad 12$$

Where j is the

Current density; and σ is the electrical conductivity, which is the reciprocal of the resistivity, ρ . For aquifer material having unit cross-sectional area A and thickness h, the two fundamental laws can combine to give

$$T = K\sigma R = \frac{KS}{\sigma} = Kh \quad \text{-----} \quad 13$$

Where T is the transmissivity, R is the transverse resistance of the aquifer, K is the hydraulic conductivity and S is the longitudinal Conductance. 46.97m.

Table 4.1 shows the values of aquifer transmissivity and the values of transverse resistance and longitudinal conductance generally known as Dar Zarrowk parameters. Aquifer transmissivities were determined using the analytical relationship established by (Niswass and Singhal 1981, Mbonu et al., 1981) between aquifer transmissivity (T_r) and transverse resistance (T) on one hand and aquifer transmissivity and longitudinal conductance (S) on the other hand. For an aquifer of electrical conductivity (σ) and hydraulic conductivity (K), the relation given in equation 1 was used

$$Tr = K\sigma T = \frac{KS}{\sigma} = KS\sigma \quad \text{-----} \quad 14$$

Based on the equation above, the quantities ($K\sigma$) and (k/σ) are assumed to be fairly constant within the watershed. Thus knowing the values of K from existing boreholes and the conductivity, the inverse of resistivity from the sounding interpretation around the borehole, one can estimate the transmissivity and its variation from place to place using the Dar zarrowk parameter determined for each aquifer. On the whole, σ or $1/\rho$ must be equivalent to any of the sets $k\sigma T$ or KS or KS/ρ to be used. For aquifer located within this study area, the mean of the hydraulic conductivity $K=8.00\text{m/day}$, while the mean transmissivity $T_r= 156.53\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ the maximum $T_r=384.80\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ while the minimum $T_r= 20.80\text{m}^2/\text{day}$. The values obtained by Uma (1989) for the Ogwashi – Asaba Formation are 1.00 to 14.00m/day for K and 54.98 to 702.60m²day for T. For the aquifers within the Benin Formation, $K_{\text{mean}} = 23.07\text{m/day}$, $T_{\text{mean}} = 704.72\text{m}^2/\text{day}$; $K_{\text{max}} = /\text{day}$; $T_{\text{max}}=2036.21\text{m}^2/\text{day}$; $K_{\text{min}} = 7.02\text{m/day}$; $T_{\text{min}} = 87.05\text{m}^2/\text{day}$. Uma, (1989) obtained K values for Benin Formation that range from a minimum of 4.90m/day to a maximum of 43.99/day with a mean of 19.71m/day. This appears to be in range constant with the values obtained in this study. The highest value of T was obtained about 200m from MOUAU gate towards the right, near the mechanic workshop. This indicates that this location has the greatest potential for productive aquifers.

Table 1: AQUIFER CHARACTERISTICS OF THE VES LOCATIONS IN THE STUDY AREA

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE	THICKNESS (CM)	AQUIFER RESISTIVITY $\rho(\Omega m)$	LONG. CONDUCTANCE $S(\Omega^{-1})$	$K\sigma(\Omega day)^{-1}$	TRANSMISSIVITY $Tr=kh$ M^2/day	ELEVATION (M)	CONDUCTIVITY(Ω^{-1})	TRANSVERSE RESISTANCE (Ωm^2)
1.	5.4799	7.5422	7.10	2862.80	0.0024	0.0027	56.80	111.56	0.00035	20325.88
2	5.4794	7.5394	6.00	7147.30	0.0008	0.0011	48.00	112.78	0.00014	42883.8
3.	5.4763	7.3418	30.00	1312.60	0.0229	0.0061	240.10	115.6	0.00076	39378
4.	5.4765	7.5398	17.00	3981.20	0.0043	0.0020	136.00	106.68	0.00025	67680.4
5.	5.4765	7.5424	21.63	3894.60	0.0056	0.0021	172.96	114.64	0.00026	84240.2
6.	5.4848	7.5476	2.60	804.40	0.0032	0.0099	20.80	136.8	0.00124	2091.44
7.	5.4803	7.5461	13.70	1716.50	0.0080	0.0047	109.60	129.54	0.00058	23516.05
8.	5.4787	7.5464	48.10	1344.70	0.0358	0.0059	384.80	136.86	0.00074	64680.07
9.	5.4831	7.5451	18.20	72840.60	0.0025	0.0011	145.60	119.99	0.000014	132579.72
10.	5.4878	7.5429	20.90	1104.80	0.0189	0.0072	167.20	139.01	0.00091	23090.32
11.	5.4885	7.5461	10.90	2268.00	0.0048	0.0035	87.20	126.46	0.00044	24721.2
12.	5.4821	7.5426	12.40	3276.10	0.0038	0.0024	99.20	121.43	0.00031	40623.64
13.	5.4816	7.5400	42.20	4649.30	0.0091	0.0017	337.60	111.56	0.00022	196200.46
14.	5.4746	7.5438	23.20	8387.60	0.0028	0.0009	185.60	91.07	0.00012	194592.32

Fig 2: Contour Map of Transmissivity in the Study Area

Figure 3 show the contour map of transverse resistance which clearly reflects a high value of 194592.32Ωm² recorded for the Bishop's house off Lihman Hall at the back of the MOUAU stadium.

Fig 3: Contour Map of Transverse Resistance

Fig 3: Contour Map of Transverse Resistance

Table 2: Result of groundwater quality analysis of samples collected from selected portions of Kwa Ibo river.

Well No.	Elevation(m)	Latitude(deg.)	Longitude(deg.)	P.H.	Suspended Solids (Mg/L)	Total Suspended Solid (Mg/L)	Temp (°C)	Turbidity (Ntu)	Conductivity (µs/cm)	Total Solids (Mg/L)
1.	114.0	5.4848	7.5361	4.97	300	800	26.9	85.3	133.4	500
2	112.1	5.4834	7.5352	6.26	900	200	25.6	81.9	121.8	1100
3.	103.9	5.4815	7.5355	5.05	500	400	27.0	83.2	250.9	900
4.	104.2	5.4893	7.5349	6.34	100	100	25.6	83.8	68.9	900
5.	101.3	5.4822	7.5352	5.00	500	100	27.0	84.5	62.3	600
6.	105.9	5.4811	7.5351	5.32	200	500	26.9	83.9	300.2	700
7.	105.5	5.4804	7.5352	4.92	400	500	26.8	82.5	322.0	900
8.	100.1	5.4802	7.5353	6.37	800	500	25.4	82.3	330.4	1300
9.	89.6	5.4801	7.5374	5.42	500	400	27.0	82.6	312.4	900
10.	81.6	5.4805	7.5353	6.34	800	400	27.0	77.8	246.2	1200
11.	100.1	5.4772	7.5351	5.32	700	600	27.0	81.3	390.4	1300

GROUNDWATER FLOW DIRECTION IN THE STUDY AREA

Hydraulic head or piezometric head is a specific measurement of water pressure above a geodetic datum. It is usually measured as a water surface elevation, expressed in units of length, at the entrance (or bottom) of a piezometer. In an aquifer, it can be calculated from the depth to water in a piezometric well (a specialized water well), and given information of the piezometric elevation and screen depth. Water entering an unconfined or confined well will stand at a particular level. This level is the hydraulic head and is actually the sum of three components, the pressure head, elevation head and velocity head. Therefore the distribution of hydraulic head through an aquifer system determines where groundwater will flow. Where the hydraulic head is constant, there is no flow. However, if there is a difference in the hydraulic head from the top to the bottom due to draining from the bottom, the water will flow downward, due to difference in heads, also called the hydraulic gradient.

Table.3: Result of groundwater quality analysis of samples collected from selected boreholes in the study area

	Locations	Elevation(m)	Latitude (deg.)	Longitude(deg.)	P.H.	Suspended Solids (Mg/L)	Total dissolved Solid (Mg/L)	Temp (°C)	Turbidity (Ntu)	Conductivity (µs/cm)	Total Solids (Mg/L)
1.	PG HOSTEL	117.3	5.4776	7.5423	4.71	350	150	26.6	98.8	100	500
2	CHAPEL (NRCRB)	123.7	7.4753	7.5438	5.09	200	100	26.7	89.2	66.7	300
3.	Eng. Block	91.2	5.4772	7.5398	6.90	250	350	26.1	90.5	233.30	600
4.	Staff School	131.6	5.4893	7.5393	6.27	350	450	26.8	86.1	300.00	800
5.	Male Hostel	122.8	5.4807	7.5421	6.81	200	600	26.4	89.6	400.00	800
6.	Admin Blk.	125.4	5.4788	7.5435	5.27	300	600	26.3	92.6	400	800
7.	VC'S Lodge	136.6	5.4852	7.5476	6.94	100	900	26.4	88.5	600	1000
8.	Zenith Bank Research	125.6	5.4848	7.5421	4.96	700	500	26.6	91.4	333.33	1200
9.	Opp. Sch. gate	127.4	5.4799	7.5464	4.98	400	400	26.8	91.8	266.7	800
10.	MPP6 Umudike	166.4	5.4719	7.5484	5.04	500	300	26.3	92.0	200.01	800
11.	CNAS	103.3	5.4809	7.5398	5.49	1200	900	26.5	88.7	600.03	2100

To determine the direction of flow of an aquifer in the study area, groundwater level measurement; relative geographic position of the wells and elevation were collected and contoured in map perspectives, (using surfer 6 and 8 software), thereby generating groundwater surface maps. The direction of groundwater movement can be understood in the fact that groundwater always flows in the direction of decreasing head. From the contour map (showing direction) from samples collected from for Kwa Ibo River fig 2, it can be inferred that the water flows downwards from the river(North) with a higher hydraulic head (elevation) towards the well (south) located within the premises of MOUAU.

Fig 4: Contour Map for Kwa River Elevation

Fig 5 : Contour Map for borehole water Elevation

Fig 6: Flow direction for Kwa Ibo river

Fig 7 : Flow direction for Borehole water

Similarly, the elevation map/direction of flow from modeling of water samples collected from borehole wells located within the MOUAAU campus and its environs indicates that water flows towards the south west direction interacting with the groundwater from the Kwa Iboe River fig4.14

The rate of movement on the other hand is dependent on the hydraulic gradient, which is the change in head per unit distance.

The modeling studies when compared with the contour maps from Kwa Ibo river water samples and that of the borehole water samples reveals that there is a river water- aquifer water interaction at a particular geographic location within the study area.

The water- table elevation in the water shed along the northern boundary was defined by the 97m (a. m. s. l.) equipotential line at Government College in the north, whereas the lowest water -table elevation was 34m at Usaga Elegu in the south (Igboekwe 2008).The top layer mostly consists of 5-120 m topsoil/laterite ,underlain by a sandy zone 68-325m thick. The aquifer permeability varied from 3.15mday^{-1} to 14.4m day^{-1} in the water shed. Higher permeability prevailed along the Kwa Ibo River course.

SUSPENDED PARTICULATE MATTER IN WATER SAMPLES.

Table 3 shows the magnitude of loaded suspended particles in the borehole water samples analyzed in the laboratory. The suspended particulates in the analyzed borehole water samples ranged from 100 to 1200mg/L with an average value of 414mg/L. In comparison with the WHO standard, this pollutant seems to fall within the acceptable WHO standard. The groundwater within the indicated depths and locations in the table does not seem to be polluted/contaminated. The suspended solids particles from river water samples were also investigated and the result is shown in table 2

The value of the suspended solids analyzed from Kwa Ibo River water samples ranged from 100 to 900 mg/L and the average value was found to be 518mg/L. Based on the flow interaction between the borehole water samples and the Kwa Ibo River samples, the borehole water seems to be polluted with the highly loaded suspended particles present in the Kwa Ibo River water samples.

By applying surfer 8 software, contour maps showing the distribution of the suspended solids were obtained as shown in figs 8 and 9 , for borehole water samples and fig. 10 and 11 for Kwa Ibo River water samples.

Kwa Ibo River according to the elevation contours in fig. 4 flows from north to south and in event acts as the main recharge of the selected boreholes in Michael Okpara University. The fairly high distribution of the suspended particles in Kwa Ibo River water samples is responsible for the high value of suspended particles in borehole water samples.

Fig 8 and 9: 2-D and 3-D contour map distribution for suspended solids in Borehole water

Fig 10 and 11: 2-D and 3-D contour maps distribution of suspended solids for Kwa Ibo River

Summary and Conclusion

The summary of the geophysical data and the complementary laboratory analysis for boreholes and the Kwa Ibo River are respectively shown in table 1, 2, and 3. The estimation of elevation from geophysical survey and within the Kwa Ibo River and boreholes has enabled us to determine the pattern and direction of flow of the groundwater. This was achievable by employing the idea that groundwater flows from topographically high elevation to a topographically low elevation. In general water flows from the northern zone (Kwa Ibo River) with higher hydraulic head to the southern zone (MOUAU) with somewhat low hydraulic head. The interpretation is that water from the river recharges the boreholes thereby causing interaction due to the contaminant loads or plumes. This interaction can be inferred from the elevation contour maps shown in Fig. 4 and 5 and the direction contour maps in 6 and 7.

In general, the combination of the geophysics and geology of the area indicated that it has lateritic topsoil, sandy soil, medium to coarse grained sand, fine to medium grained sand, medium grained sand, clayey sand, shaley sand and river sand with various thickness at various depths. These primary parameters were used to determine the secondary parameters such as Dar Zarrouk parameters (Transverse resistance and longitudinal conductance) and electrical conductivity. With the help of the unique hydraulic conductivity determined by Igboekwe et al; 2008. The contour maps of some of these parameters were drawn to show the extent of distributions in the mapped area. The higher values of resistivities of the aquifers indicate that the aquifer itself is not contaminated. Moreover, the lower values of $K\sigma$ indicate that the water is not brackish. However, the observed contamination is due to the steady flow and interaction between the boreholes and the Kwa Iboe River that has the loaded contamination plumes.

The analysis of the borehole water at the MOUAU gave values for suspended solids, total dissolved solids, Turbidity, Conductivity, PH, and total solids. Temperature and elevation at different locations were also determined (see table 3). According to W.H.O standard the values of the suspended solids in mg/L indicates that the borehole at college of Natural and Applied Science (CNAS) and Zenith bank are somehow contaminated since the value is beyond the safe standard value. Moreover, the dissolved values of solids at CNAS, Zenith bank and VC's lodge indicates that the borehole is also contaminated. However, the reduced value of total suspended solids at the VC's lodge should not be a surprise as the VC's lodge is about 2km away from the Kwa Ibo River.

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